

Integrative Ayurvedic Management of Female Infertility Resulting in Successful Conception: A Case Report

Dr. Shakshi¹, Dr. Soni Kumari^{2*}, Dr. Monika Khatri³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Prasuti Tantra Evam Stree Roga, Patanjali Bhartiya Ayurvedigyan & Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar

²PG Scholar, Department of Prasuti Tantra Evam Stree Roga, Patanjali Bhartiya Ayurvedigyan & Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar

³PG Scholar, Department of Prasuti Tantra Evam Stree Roga, Patanjali Bhartiya Ayurvedigyan & Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Soni Kumari

ABSTRACT:

Background: Infertility is a multifactorial condition, with unexplained cases posing therapeutic challenges. Ayurveda considers it under *Yonivyapada* due to *Dosha* imbalance.

Case Presentation: A 30-year-old female presented with primary infertility, irregular cycles, dysmenorrhea, and right ovarian cyst.

Intervention: She was treated with an Ayurvedic protocol including *Dashmoola Kwath*, *Raj Pravartini Vati*, *Kumariyasava*, Churna (*Putrajivak*, *Shatavari Churna*, *Shivlingi* and *Shudha Konch*) and *Phal Ghrit*.

Results: Marked improvement in menstrual irregularity and symptoms was observed. The patient conceived within three months.

Conclusion: Ayurvedic management may provide an effective and holistic approach in managing unexplained infertility.

KEYWORDS : Infertility, *Yoni roga*, *Shatavar Churna*, Conceive.

INTRODUCTION

Infertility is defined as a failure to conceive within one or more years of regular unprotected coitus.^[1] Primary infertility denotes those patients who have never conceived. Secondary infertility indicates previous pregnancy but failure to conceive subsequently.^[2] Prevalence of infertility is about 10-15% in couples of reproductive age group. About 80% of women conceive within 1 year of marriage and 90% within 2 years.^[3] Conception depends on the fertility potential of both the male and female partner. The male is directly responsible in about 30-40 percent, the female in about 40-55 percent and both are responsible in about 10 percent cases. The remaining 10 percent, is unexplained.^[4]

In our classics, *Acharya Charak* have given the causes of *Yonivyapada*. These are *Mithyachar*, *Pradushta artava*, *Bijadosha* and *Daiva* which ultimately leads to infertility. *Acharya Sushrut* mention that the *Vata* is aggravated and alongwith vitiaed *Pitta* and *Kapha* reaches the *Yoni Pradesha* causing *Yoni rogas*. These *rogas* are caused due to indulgence in improper diet and regimen, *artava dosha*(ovulatory factors or menstrual

disorders or hormonal causes), *bija* (seminal pathology), *daiva*(idiopathic).^[5] *Madhukosha* elaborates *dushtartava* means *artava/rajas* vitiated by *vatadi dosha* e.g. *Vandhya* etc. are due to vitiation of *artava* by *doshas*, *bija dosha* means both male and female gametes.^[6]

This case study examines unexplained infertility and its management in accordance with the treatment protocols described by *Acharyas* in *classical Samhitas*.

CASE REPORT

A 30 year old married woman came to *Prasuti Tantra Evam Stree Roga* OPD on 19/08/2024 with complains of not getting conceived after 1 year of unprotected coitus. She also had complaint about delayed and painful menses since 6 month. On USG, she was detected to have Right Ovarian Simple Cyst. She took allopathic treatment but got no relief, So she came to Patanjali Ayurvedic Medical Hospital Haridwar for ayurvedic treatment.

MENSTRUAL HISTORY

Age of Menarche	13 year
Last Menstrual Period(LMP)	18/08/2024
Previous Menstrual Period(PMP)	02/07/2024
Duration of Bleeding	3-4days
Interval of Bleeding	45-50 days
Amount of Bleeding	3-4 pads/day
Dysmenorrhea	Present
Clots	Present

OBSTETRICAL HISTORY : P0L0

CONTRACEPTIVE HISTORY : None

General Examination :

Built – Normal

Height - 5 ft 3 inch

Weight- 55 kg

Pulse Rate-80/min

Blood Pressure- 120/80 mm Hg

Respiratory Rate - 18/min

Temperature- 98.4 F

GYNECOLOGICAL EXAMINATION :

Per Speculum : Healthy Cervix

Per Vaginum : Uterus anteverted, normal in size and no fornix tenderness.

Dashvidha Pariksha:

Prakriti- PittaKaphaja

Sara - Rasa

Samhanana- Madhyama

Pramana - Sama

Satmya- Madhyama

Satva- Avara

Vaya- Madhyamavastha

Vyayama Shakti- Madhyama

Ahara Shakti – Madhyama

Jarana Shakti - Madhyama

Ashtavidha Pariksha:

Nadi- Vata, Pitta dominant

Mala- Sama

Mutra- Samanya

Jihwa- Alipta (clear)

Shabda- Spashta

Sparsha- Anushnasheeta

Drika- Samanya

Akriti- Madhyama

INVESTIGATIONS

FEMALE	MALE
Hb- 11.5 g/dL	Hb- 15.1 g/dL
Blood Group – ‘B’ positive	Blood Group – ‘B’ positive
TSH – 2.0 mIU / L	HSA- Count- 35.46 million/ml
Prolactin- 20 ng/mL	Motility – 70% motile sperms

TREATMENT PROTOCOL

Dashmoola Kwath	100 ml BD after meal
Raj Pravartini Vati	2 Tab. BD after meal
Vridhivadhika Vati	1 Tab. BD after meal
Kumariyasava	4 TSF with lukewarm water BD
Phal Ghrit	1 TSF with milk
Shatavar Churna Shivlingi Churna Shuddha Konch churna Putrajivak Churna	Take 4 powders mixed together 125 mg BD with lukewarm water

RESULT

After administration of the planned *Ayurvedic* treatment protocol, the patient showed marked improvement in clinical symptoms. The menstrual cycle became more regular with reduced interval (from 35–45 days to near normal), and dysmenorrhea significantly decreased. Associated symptoms such as clot passage were also reduced.

After continuation of medicine, the patient achieved spontaneous conception within three months of treatment. Pregnancy was confirmed by a positive urine pregnancy test and subsequently by ultrasonography. This outcome indicates successful restoration of reproductive function and highlights the efficacy of the *Ayurvedic* intervention in the management of infertility.

DISCUSSION

Dashmoola^[7] Kwath - It acts primarily by balancing *Apana Vata*, which regulates ovulation and reproductive functions. Its anti-inflammatory (*Shothahara*) and analgesic (*Vedanasthapana*) properties help reduce pelvic inflammation and dysmenorrhea. It also improves *Artava* formation and normalizes menstrual cycle, creating a favorable environment for conception. Thus, it supports ovulation, fertilization, and implantation.

Shivlingi - *Shivlingi* promotes fertility and normalizes the menstrual cycle. It reduces blockage of several channels in the body by clearing the excess *Kapha* and *Aam*.^[8]

Putrajivak - ‘*Putram garbham jeevayati , Putrajiva*’

Due to *madhur rasa*, *madhur vipak*, *sheet veerya*, it acts as *garbhauptadak*, *garbhastapak*, *garbhavridhikar* so it provides jeevan to the *garbha*.^[9]

Shatavari Churna^[10], a powerful phytoestrogenic *Rasayana*, nourishes the *Artava dhatu* and supports follicle maturation.

Shudha Konch - It pacifies *Vata* and *Kapha doshas*. It enhances fertility, regulates menstrual cycles, and supports ovulation.

Phal ghrita^[11] - It is prepared using *Ghrita* as a base along with multiple herbs such as *Shatavari*, *Ashwagandha*, *Lodhra*, *Gokshura*, and *Triphala*, which are known for their *Vrishya*, *Garbhasthapaka*, and *Rasayana* properties.

Vridhivadhika Vati^[12] have *Lekhana* and *Shothahara* properties that help resolve cystic formations and abnormal tissue growth, thereby restoring normal ovarian physiology.

Kumariyasava^[13] acts as a uterine tonic and promotes *Artava* production, aiding in regular menstruation and enhancing endometrial receptivity through its *Agni-deepana* and hormone-regulating effects.

The synergistic action of these formulations results in hormonal balance, cyst reduction, improved folliculogenesis, and enhanced uterine receptivity, ultimately creating a favorable environment for conception. The successful outcome in this case can be attributed to this holistic and multi-targeted Ayurvedic approach addressing both systemic and local factors of infertility.

REFERENCES

1. Dutta DC. Textbook of gynecology. 9th ed. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers; 2023.
2. Dutta DC. Textbook of gynecology. 9th ed. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers; 2023.
3. Babu SA. Clinical obstetrics and gynecology. 2nd ed. New Delhi: Wolters Kluwer; 2021.
4. Dutta DC. Textbook of gynecology. 9th ed. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers; 2023.
5. Sushruta Samhita. Uttara Tantra. 38th chapter, verses 3–6. In: Shastri AD, editor. Sushruta Samhita with Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; 2014.
6. Madhava Nidana. Chapter 62, verse 1. In: Shastri YG, editor. Madhava Nidana with Madhukosha Commentary. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; 2012.
7. Bhisagratna, G.D. (2016), English Translation by Lochan, K. *Bhaisajya Ratnavali*, Vol. I. New Delhi: Chaukhamba Publications; Chapter 05. p. 165-166
8. Sharma, V.B., Soni, M.K., Onkar, J.M., & Sharma, O. (2019). Uses of Shivlingi seed (*Bryonia laciniosa* Atleck. & Hemsli.) in female infertility: A review article. World journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 5(9), 88
9. Malty, S., & Majumdar, D. (2024). Putrajeevaka as a matrudharak. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 13(5), 605.
10. Bhavamishra. Bhavaprakasha Nighantu. Guduchayadi Varga (Shatavari). Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Bhawan; Reprint ed.

11. Government of India, Ministry of AYUSH. *The Ayurvedic Formulary of India*. Part I. 2nd ed. New Delhi: Ministry of AYUSH; 2003.
12. Govinda Das Sen. Bhaishajya Ratnavali. 1st ed. (reprint). Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; 2017. Vriddhi Roga Adhikara.
13. Govinda Das Sen. Bhaishajya Ratnavali. 1st ed. (reprint). Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; 2017. Asava Arishta Prakarana (Kumaryasava)
14. Bhisagratna, G.D. (2016), English Translation by
15. Lochan, K. Bhaisajya Ratnavali, Vol. I. New Delhi:
16. Chaukhamba Publications; Chapter 05. p. 165-166
17. Bhisagratna, G.D. (2016), English Translation by
18. Lochan, K. Bhaisajya Ratnavali, Vol. I. New Delhi:
19. Chaukhamba Publications; Chapter 05. p. 165-166